

Osemosys Modelling Training in Ghana

Energy Modeling for Sustainable Future Energy Mix for Zambia: Response to Climate Change and Global Warming
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@2024

Table of Contents

List of Figures	2
Keywords	2
Acknowledgments	2
Executive Summary	2
1. Introduction	2
1.1 Purpose and Scope	2
1.2 Objective and Aims	3
1.3 Main Challenge(s) Investigated with Model	3
1.4 Research Questions	4
2. Methodology	4
2.1 Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented	4
2.2 Data sources	4
2.2.1 Overview of ZESCO	5
2.2.2 Other Power Producers in Zambia	5
2.2.3 Role of the National Grid	5
2.3 Scenarios and Assumptions	5
2.3.1 Business As Usual (BAU) Scenario: 100% Electricity Access	5
2.3.2 Energy Security Scenario (ESS): 75 Percent Electric Car Usage	6
2.3.3 Energy Transition Scenario (ETS): 100% Electricity Access and High Electric Car Usage	6
2.3.4 Summary of the Scenarios	6
3. Results	6
3.1 Power Generation	6
3.2 Total Annual Capacity	7
3.3 Capital Cost	8
3.4 Total Emissions	9
4. Discussion (300-700 words)	9
4.1 Power Generation	9
4.2 Total Annual Capacity	10
4.3 Capital Cost	11
4.4 Total Emissions	12
4.5 Implications for Policy and Planning	13
5. Conclusion	13
References	14
Appendices	14

List of Figures

Figure 1: Power Generation for the Three Scenarios	7
Figure 2: Total Annual Capacity for the Three Scenarios	8
Figure 3: Capital Cost for the Three Scenarios	8
Figure 4: Total Emissions by Scenario	9

Keywords

Energy; Renewable; Non-renewable; Generation; OseMosys; Scenario; Mix; Technology

Acknowledgments

This report was created as a result of the engagement with the trainers organized by Climate Compatible Growth (CCG). Other key stakeholders included, the United Nations Energy Commission for Africa, Ministry of Energy Ghana, the Ghana Energy Commission, Ghana Atomic Energy Commission, Ghana Institute of Management and Public Administration, and The Brew-Hammond Energy Centre at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology as the organizers of the EMP-A. Furthermore, we thank CCG for funding this training.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Executive Summary

The Business As Usual (BAU), Energy Security Scenario (ESS), and Energy Transition Scenario (ETS) collectively highlight Zambia's commitment to achieving 100 percent electricity access and substantial electric vehicle (EV) adoption by 2050. Each scenario envisions significant investments in renewable energy and infrastructure, aiming to enhance energy security, reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and promote sustainable energy production. The BAU, ESS, and ETS scenarios provide distinct yet complementary pathways for Zambia's energy and transportation future. The findings show that, ETS scenario has the highest energy generation, installed capacity and cumulative investment costs whereas, BAU has the highest GHG emission as compared to the other scenarios. These findings are essential for strategic planning and investment. Therefore collaboration are essential to achieving a sustainable and prosperous energy future for Zambia, with a strong emphasis on maximizing the use of renewable energy sources to balance energy access, environmental sustainability, and economic feasibility.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

Energy demand has been rising due to economic activity in Zambia particularly in the mining, manufacturing, and agriculture sectors. According to the Ministry of Finance, Zambia's economy has been growing at an average of 5 percent per annum over the past 10 years (Kaunda, et al., 2013). Strategic utilization and development of Zambia's energy sources can increase industry competitiveness, improve rural service delivery, and reduce rural poverty with an inclination towards renewable energy. Renewable energy resources offer greater opportunities for a transition towards sustainable development. To achieve national energy access targets of 66 percent by 2035 (90 percent urban & 51 percent Rural) and contribute to a diversified energy mix to create increased energy security at affordable prices, the Zambian government is planning to diversify the electricity generation sector by including both renewable and nonrenewable energy resources. Among the renewable energy resources include wind, solar, biomass, geothermal, and hydro in the electricity sector (Ministry of Finance and National Planning, 2022). With regards to nonrenewable energy, the country has already started on the trajectory of coal energy production through Maamba Collieries of which 300 megawatts are produced to the national grid. Furthermore, the government plans to bring on board various policies to speed up the renewable energy systems implementation in the country. However, to achieve such targets it is essential for various policymakers including the government to identify which renewable energy resource combination would provide the greatest benefit in order to achieving sustainable electricity generation diversification in the country by 2030 in order to achieve the vision 2030. The geographical position of Zambia gives it a comparative advantage of Solar energy production due to the abundance of sunlight in the southern-central part of Africa (Kaunda, et al., 2013).

With regards to Electric Vehicles, Zambia and DRC are on the quest to implement an Innovative transboundary battery and Electric vehicle Special Economic Zone. This is in line with a future trajectory of promoting Electric Vehicles in both countries as they try to eliminate the usage of fossil fuel. The establishment of a transboundary battery and Electric Vehicle Special Economic Zone between Zambia and the DRC is a forward-thinking initiative with the potential to transform the energy and transportation sectors of both countries (United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, 2024). By focusing on the production of EVs and batteries, harnessing local resources, and creating a supportive infrastructure and regulatory environment, this initiative aims to reduce fossil fuel dependence, promote sustainable development, and drive economic growth. With strong government support, international collaboration, and a commitment to sustainability, Zambia and the DRC can position themselves as leaders in the African electric vehicle revolution.

1.2 Objective and Aims

Assess and identify the sustainable future electricity generation mix for Zambia using the Osemosys modeling approach under the effects of Climate Change and Global Warming

1.3 Main Challenge(s) Investigated with Model

1. Lack of access to clean and affordable electricity in Zambia
2. Increase in Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emission in transport and domestic sector
3. Climate Change and its effect on generation

1.4 Research Questions

1. How do increases in the access to clean & affordable electricity in Zambia impact the future energy mix for the nation?
2. What is the impact of transitioning to e-vehicles on the future energy mix and GHG emission in Zambia?
3. What is the impact of transitioning to e-vehicles and 100% access to electricity on the future energy mix and GHG emission in Zambia?
4. How do Zambia mitigate climate change and its effects on generation?

2. Methodology

2.1 Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented

The study used OSeMOSYS to perform a long-term analysis of the sustainability of the electricity generation mix. And the model can simulate a wide range of technologies for electricity generation, including fossil fuels, nuclear, and various renewable energy sources like wind, solar, hydro, and biomass. It also considers different resource availability and technological advancements over time. Also, the technology is capable of long-term planning, often extending several decades into the future. It can provide detailed temporal resolution, typically breaking down the analysis into multiple time periods (e.g., annually, seasonally, or even hourly) to capture variations in demand and supply. The model also provides a robust framework for analyzing and planning the evolution of the electricity generation mix. Its ability to simulate a wide array of technologies and policies makes it an invaluable tool for stakeholders aiming to achieve a sustainable, cost-effective, and reliable energy future.

2.2 Data sources

The study drew its sample from the entire country which is serviced by the Zambia Electricity Supply Corporation Limited (ZESCO). ZESCO is a state-owned power company in Zambia. It is Zambia's largest power company producing about 80 percent of the electricity consumed in the country. Other producing power companies in Zambia include Lunsemfwa Hydropower, Mulungushi Hydropower, and Maamba Collieries which all supply to the national grid which is managed by ZESCO. This makes ZESCO a critical entity in Zambia's energy sector.

2.2.1 Overview of ZESCO

It is a State-Owned Enterprise and operates under the jurisdiction of the Zambian government. It is tasked with the generation, transmission, distribution, and supply of electricity throughout Zambia. ZESCO's dominant position underscores its importance in ensuring the country's energy security and stability. Furthermore, ZESCO manages the national electricity grid, which involves overseeing the transmission of electricity from various power plants to consumers across the country. This centralized control ensures the coordinated distribution of electricity and the maintenance of grid reliability.

2.2.3 Role of the National Grid

The national grid, managed by ZESCO, is a critical infrastructure that enables the distribution of electricity from various power generation sources to consumers across the country. It ensures that electricity generated by both ZESCO and independent power producers (such as Lunsemfwa Hydropower, Mulungushi Hydropower, and Maamba Collieries) is efficiently transmitted and distributed. This centralized management of the grid helps maintain a balance between supply and demand, ensuring that different regions of Zambia receive a stable and continuous supply of electricity.

By drawing its sample from the entire country serviced by ZESCO, the study captures a comprehensive view of Zambia's electricity consumption and generation dynamics. ZESCO's dominant role, coupled with the contributions from other power producers, highlights a diverse and interconnected energy sector. This structure supports the reliability and sustainability of electricity supply in Zambia, which is essential for the country's economic growth and development.

2.3 Scenarios and Assumptions

The Government of Zambia plans to increase access to electricity to 66% from 41% by 2030 and 100% by 2050 to reduce deforestation and improve the standard of living of the population. Furthermore, the government plans to adopt e-vehicles in the transport sector to improve energy security, combat climate change (reduction in greenhouse gas emission) and support environmental sustainability. Therefore, this study aims at assessing and identifying the sustainable future energy mix for Zambia with emphasis on 100% transition to e-vehicle and 100% access to electricity while considering availability of local energy resources. The study have adopted three scenarios to achieve the objectives, namely;

- Business As Usual (BAU) with regards to access to electricity reaching at 100 percent for the entire population of the country.
- Energy Security Scenario (ESS); The second scenario is that of the Energy Security Scenario (ESS) with regards to having electric car usage of at least 75 percent of the entire population.
- Energy Transition Scenario (ETS): finally, the third scenario is that of Energy Transition Scenario (ETS) of which entails both the usage of Electric Cars as well as that of access to electricity both in urban and rural areas reaching a 100 percent.

2.3.1 Business As Usual (BAU) Scenario: 100% Electricity Access

In the Business As Usual (BAU) scenario, the goal is to achieve 100 percent access to electricity for the entire population of Zambia. This scenario assumes a continuation of current policies and practices, with incremental improvements to expand electricity access without major deviations from the current trajectory. This scenario will be achieved through infrastructure development by grid expansion reaching unserved and underserved areas. Furthermore, a continuation of the Rural Electrification Program to meet even the remotest parts of the country. Furthermore, the BAU will also include the aspects of policy support such as those that support the expansion of electricity access, including subsidies and incentives for infrastructure development. And also, the engagement of collaboration between the public sector, private companies, and international organizations to fund and implement electrification projects.

2.3.2 Energy Security Scenario (ESS): 75 Percent Electric Car Usage

The Energy Security Scenario (ESS) envisions a future where 75 percent of the Zambian population uses electric cars. This scenario emphasizes the transition to electric mobility as a means of enhancing energy security and reducing dependence on imported fossil fuels as well as a critical reduction in GHG emissions. This will be achieved through infrastructure and technological development. For instance, the development of charging infrastructure both for public and private usages will eventually support the adoption of electric vehicles. The assumption is that through this the country will have both environmental and economic benefits such as a significant reduction in greenhouse gas emissions from the transportation sector and reduced dependence on imported oil, enhancing national energy security.

2.3.3 Energy Transition Scenario (ETS): 100% Electricity Access and High Electric Car Usage

The Energy Transition Scenario (ETS) combines the objectives of achieving 100 percent electricity access and high adoption of electric cars. This scenario represents a comprehensive approach to transforming Zambia's energy landscape. This can be achieved through urban and rural electrification, renewable energy integration, the creation of electric mobility infrastructure, and leveraging advancements in both electricity generation and E-vehicle technologies to ensure efficiency and sustainability.

2.3.4 Summary of the Scenarios

The three scenarios the Business As Usual (BAU), the Energy Security Scenario (ESS), and the Energy Transition Scenario (ETS), outline distinct pathways for Zambia's energy future. The BAU scenario focuses on achieving universal electricity access through incremental improvements. The ESS emphasizes the adoption of electric vehicles to enhance energy security and reduce emissions. The ETS combines the goals of both scenarios, aiming for comprehensive energy transformation with universal electricity access and high E-vehicle adoption. Each scenario presents unique opportunities and challenges, requiring tailored strategies and coordinated efforts to achieve sustainable and inclusive energy development in Zambia.

3. Results

3.1 Power Generation

Concerning power generation, the country sees a growing trajectory in the investment of power by 2050. There is heavy dependency on hydropower generation with considerable investments in onshore wind production by 2050. Furthermore, due to the availability of coal reserves in Zambia and relative lower initial investment cost of coal power plants, despite the contribution of coal power plants to the future energy mix decreasing in 2040 it can be noted that in BAU and ETS scenarios, after 2040 coal power generation continue contributing to the future energy mix up to 2050. Figure 1 below highlights the findings of these three scenarios with ETS having the highest power generation followed by BAU and EES scenario being least among the scenarios.

Figure 1: Power Generation for the Three Scenarios

3.2 Total Annual Capacity

Figure 2 below shows the total annual power capacity required to meet the future projected total annual demand. It can be observed that EAS has the highest expected installed capacity followed by BAU and EES being least. This is due to increased demand from increased access to electricity and increased adoption of e-vehicles. It can be further be noted that large hydro and onshore has the highest installed capacity up to 2050 in all scenarios. However, solar PV has considerable installed capacity. The results for the three scenarios are depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Total Annual Capacity for the Three Scenarios

3.3 Capital Cost

There is a dwindling total annual capital investment cost in hydropower by 2050 with coal having been removed completely from investment in EES scenario. Furthermore, solar PV and onshore wind investment by 2040 is considerable in both BAU and ETS scenarios. In terms of total cumulative investment cost for entire planning period, it was observed that ETS scenarios requires highest investments followed by BAU scenario and EES scenario having the least among the scenarios as depicted in Figure 3. This higher total cumulative capital investment cost for ETS scenario is generally due to expected higher demand in this scenario from increased access to electricity and adoption of e-vehicles.

Figure 3: Capital Cost for the Three Scenarios

3.4 Total Emissions

The emissions in the three scenarios are depicted differently with BAU having the highest emissions followed by EAS and Lastly EES. As observed from all scenarios in figure 4, CO2 emission will continue increasing despite introduction of renewable energy in the future energy mix. This is due to importation of coal energy but also introduction of Biomass in the future energy mix. The CO2 emissions for the three scenarios are depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Total Emissions by Scenario

4. Discussion

4.1 Power Generation

The power generation results by 2050, are indicative that the scenarios of Business As Usual (BAU), Energy Security Scenario (ESS), and Energy Transition Scenario (ETS) all show significant progress in power access and the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) in Zambia. The shared goals of these scenarios include achieving 100 percent electricity access for all households and attaining at least 75 percent EV usage, supported by strategic investments in hydropower and renewable energy sources. This is also in line with Zambia's Eighth National Development Plan (ENDP) (Ministry of Finance and National Planning, 2022). Additionally, these scenarios envision a substantial reduction in coal and petroleum use, leading to cleaner energy production and reduced greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. In terms of each of the scenarios, the BAU is indicative of gradually expanding electricity access with the integration of renewable energy sources. With this in place, we see grid expansion by 2050, as well as an investment in off grid solutions such as solar home systems and mini-grids to provide access to the remotest parts of the country through Rural Electrification Authority (REA). In line with the adoption and usage of EVs, achieving 75 percent EV usage is facilitated by extensive charging infrastructure and favorable policies as indicated in the results. Furthermore, this has brought about a lack of dependence on fossil fuels by 2050 henceforth meeting national energy security and climate mitigation. With the third scenario, the ETS envisions a comprehensive transformation of Zambia's energy landscape, combining universal electricity access with high EV adoption rates as indicated in Figure 1. Others are indicative of the widespread Usage of EVs reaching a 75 percent adoption rate for EVs, supported by a robust and extensive charging network. Furthermore, this can also be supported by a strong policy framework, including subsidies, tax incentives, and regulatory support for EVs and charging infrastructure. With the diverse energy mix that is indicated in Figure 1, the use of EV's is made more efficient.

4.2 Total Annual Capacity

The annual capacity factor is the amount of energy a generating plant (e.g., a wind farm) produces over the year divided by the amount of energy that would have been produced if the plant had been running at full capacity during that same time interval. As such from the results as indicated in Figure 2, BAU and EAS have more annual capacity by 2070 as compared to EES which is an indication of lack of investment in EES. However, it should be noted that there is not much difference in three scenarios across the years. This is an indication of consistency in investment to access to electricity and that of Electric Vehicles respectively. Furthermore, the capacity is inclined towards renewable energy as such contributing to the reduction in the GHG and as such contributing to the mitigation of climate change.

In evaluating the annual capacity factors for the Business As Usual (BAU), Energy Security Scenario (ESS), and Energy Transition Scenario (ETS), it is evident from the results indicated in Figure 2 that both BAU and ETS scenarios exhibit higher annual capacity by 2070 compared to the ESS scenario. This difference is

primarily attributed to the level of investment in energy infrastructure and technologies across these scenarios. However, the relatively small differences in capacity factors over the years suggest a consistent approach to investments in electricity access and electric vehicle (EV) infrastructure. It should also be noted that the annual capacity factor is a crucial metric that measures the efficiency and productivity of a generating plant.

It should also be noted that both BAU and ETS scenarios show higher annual capacity by 2050 reflecting substantial investments in energy generation capacity, particularly in renewable energy sources such as wind, solar, and hydropower. These scenarios focus on diversifying the energy mix by incorporating various types of energy technologies in all the three scenarios results in more efficient and reliable energy production.

- However, the lower total cumulative installed capacity presented in EES scenario indicates comparatively less investment in energy generation infrastructure. This may be due to a more focused investment in EV alone including energy security measures.

Concerning electricity access, in all three scenarios, there is a consistent investment in expanding electricity access. This is evidenced by the gradual increase in capacity factors over the years, showing ongoing efforts to connect more households to the grid. This is also reflected in policies and programs such as that of REA which supports rural electrification and the deployment of off-grid solutions such as solar home systems to ensure that even remote areas gain access to reliable electricity. In EES future scenario, apart from electricity access in homes based on lower access levels, investment in EV infrastructure should be consistent across the scenarios, reflecting the commitment to transitioning away from fossil fuels and promoting cleaner transportation options. This will eventually translate into the development of charging networks, incentives for EV adoption, and public awareness campaigns to contribute to the growing penetration of EVs, aiming for 75 percent usage by 2050.

Important and consistent to the objective of this study, is the focus on renewable energy sources which is a common thread in all three scenarios, with significant investments in solar, wind, and hydropower. This mix is ensuring the transition towards renewables and as such is crucial for reducing reliance on coal and petroleum, thereby decreasing GHG emissions and mitigating climate change impacts.

4.3 Capital Cost

Capital costs are fixed, one-time expenses incurred on the purchase of land, buildings, construction, and equipment used in the production of goods or in the rendering of services. As such it is no surprise from the results that the EAS scenario has more investment followed by the BAU and then ESS. This is so because the EAS scenario is a combination of two aspects: that of access and that of EV, hence needing more investment as compared to the other two. Having access of 100 percent to electricity also requires more investment as compared to the creation of EV hence the reason why BAU has more investment as compared to ESS as depicted in Figure 3.

These costs are a critical consideration in planning and implementing large-scale energy and infrastructure projects. In the context of the Business As Usual (BAU), Energy Security Scenario (ESS), and Energy Transition Scenario (ETS), the differences in capital costs as shown in Figure 3 reflect the scope and scale of investments required to achieve their respective goals. The EAS scenario aims to achieve both 100 percent electricity access and significant EV adoption. As such there is extensive investment in expanding the grid, building new power plants (including renewable sources), and deploying off-grid solutions for remote areas. At the same time development of EV charging stations, manufacturing facilities for EVs, and supporting technologies such as battery production and recycling facilities. Henceforth, the dual focus on electricity access and EV adoption results in the highest capital costs among the three scenarios. This includes significant expenditures on renewable energy projects, grid infrastructure, and transportation infrastructure.

When it comes to the BAU scenario, it prioritizes achieving 100 percent electricity access without a specific emphasis on EV adoption. Hence the major investments are in expanding the grid and increasing power generation capacity, including both conventional and renewable energy sources. Through grid expansion it ensures that all households, particularly in rural and underserved areas, are connected to the grid. While substantial, the capital costs in terms of investments are lower than the EAS scenario because the focus is solely on electricity access, not on EV infrastructure.

The ESS scenario focuses on reducing emissions through the widespread adoption of EVs while ensuring energy security. In this scenario, the EV infrastructure is the major investment which ensures investments in renewable energy sources to ensure that the additional electricity demand from EVs is met sustainably. As such it is with no surprise that unlike the BAU scenario, the ESS does not focus on achieving universal electricity access, thus requiring lower overall investment in grid expansion and rural electrification.

4.4 Total Emissions

The emissions profiles of the Business As Usual (BAU), Energy Security Scenario (ESS), and Energy Transition Scenario (ETS) reflect the differing approaches and priorities in achieving energy and transportation goals by 2050. The BAU scenario, which focuses heavily on achieving 100 percent electricity access through conventional means, results in higher emissions compared to the ESS and ETS scenarios. The ESS scenario significantly reduces emissions by replacing gasoline vehicles with electric vehicles (EVs), while the ETS scenario, despite its similarities to the ESS, incurs slightly higher emissions due to the added emphasis on universal electricity access. The BAU scenario requires substantial energy production to achieve 100 percent electricity access. This involves expanding the grid and increasing power generation capacity as such explains the higher emission among the three scenarios. Furthermore, the reliance on conventional energy sources, including fossil fuels, contributes to higher greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. As more households gain access to electricity, the increased demand is often met with a mix of energy sources, including coal, oil, and natural

gas, which are significant GHG emitters. Even with investments in renewable energy, the BAU scenario's extensive energy needs result in higher overall emissions.

When it comes to the ESS scenario it emphasizes reducing emissions by replacing up to 75 percent of gasoline-powered vehicles with EVs, which produce nearly zero pollutants. This shift from internal combustion engine vehicles to EVs drastically cuts down emissions from the transportation sector, one of the largest contributors to GHG emissions. The elimination of a substantial portion of gasoline emissions leads to a marked reduction in total GHG emissions, as evidenced in Figure 4. The focus on EV infrastructure and renewable energy sources further supports this reduction. The ETS scenario combines the goals of the ESS with the aim of achieving universal electricity access, similar to the BAU scenario. While the replacement of gasoline vehicles with EVs is a key component, the push for 100 percent electricity access necessitates additional energy production. However, the ETS scenario's emissions are similar to the ESS scenario due to the significant reduction in transportation-related emissions, but the drive for universal electricity access introduces additional emissions from the increased energy demand, even if renewable sources are predominantly used.

In summary, it can be agreed that the BAU scenario's higher emissions stem from its extensive energy production requirements, which are not fully offset by renewable energy investments. Both ESS and ETS scenarios achieve significant emission reductions through the widespread adoption of EVs and renewable energy sources.

4.5 Implications for Policy and Planning

With regards to policy and planning, there is a need for strategic investment allocation about the EAS Scenario, policymakers and planners need to allocate substantial funds to both the energy and transportation sectors. This requires a balanced approach to ensure that both goals, universal electricity access, and high EV adoption—are met efficiently. In the BAU Scenario, there is a need for focused investment in electricity infrastructure which can help achieve universal access, but planners must be cautious of the potential environmental impact due to reliance on conventional energy sources if not adequately balanced with renewable investments. And in the ESS Scenario, investments should be directed toward establishing a robust EV infrastructure and increasing the share of renewable energy in the power mix. This scenario requires careful planning to ensure that energy security is maintained while minimizing capital costs.

5. Conclusion

The BAU, ESS, and ETS scenarios collectively highlight Zambia's commitment to achieving 100 percent electricity access and substantial EV adoption by 2050. These scenarios envision significant investments in renewable energy and infrastructure, leading to cleaner energy production, reduced GHG emissions, and enhanced energy security. While each scenario presents unique pathways, they all underscore the importance of strategic planning, investment, and collaboration to realize a sustainable and prosperous energy future for Zambia.

■

The analysis of annual capacity factors and investment patterns in the BAU, ESS, and ETS scenarios highlights a commitment to expanding electricity access and promoting EV adoption. While the ESS scenario shows relatively lower capacity factors due to focused investments in energy security measures, the overall consistency in investment across all scenarios ensures steady progress toward achieving universal electricity access and significant EV usage by 2070. The emphasis on renewable energy sources plays a pivotal role in reducing GHG emissions, contributing to climate change mitigation, and fostering a sustainable energy future for Zambia.

The analysis of capital costs across the BAU, ESS, and EAS scenarios highlights the varying levels of investment required to achieve different energy and transportation goals. The EAS scenario demands the highest capital investment due to its comprehensive approach to electricity access and EV adoption. The BAU scenario, while primarily focused on universal electricity access, incurs significant costs but less than the EAS due to the absence of substantial EV infrastructure investments. The ESS scenario, with its emphasis on EV adoption and renewable energy, requires the lowest capital costs but still demands considerable investment in EV and renewable energy infrastructure. Policymakers must carefully consider these investment requirements and their implications for achieving sustainable and equitable energy futures.

The BAU, ESS, and ETS scenarios provide distinct pathways for Zambia's energy and transportation future, each with its own implications for GHG emissions. The BAU scenario's focus on achieving 100 percent electricity access results in higher emissions due to the extensive energy demand. In contrast, the ESS scenario achieves significant emission reductions by replacing gasoline vehicles with EVs. The ETS scenario, while sharing similarities with the ESS in terms of transportation emissions, experiences slightly higher emissions due to the additional energy required for universal electricity access. Ultimately, the choice of scenario will depend on balancing the goals of energy access, environmental sustainability, and economic feasibility, with a strong emphasis on maximizing the use of renewable energy sources to mitigate climate change impacts.

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